

Technologies and interdisciplinarity to rescue cultural heritage

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Abstract

It is strategic to establish a bridge between society and engineering education. Tec de Monterrey's Educational Model is based on disciplinary and transversal competencies, and Challenge-Based Learning. A humanistic training course with transversal competencies was designed for engineering careers; students applied various information technologies to recover and promote the cultural heritage of Monterrey, Mexico. The methodology to validate this innovation was based on the research assumption - not hypothesis -: "Students will develop to a greater extent the transversal competencies integrated to their curriculum by applying technology to recover and promote the cultural heritage of the city". The assumption was demonstrated and validated by investigating the level of development and assessment of these transversal competencies with Olivares (2018) instrument and two others with qualitative and quantitative approaches. The general objective was: Incorporate the use of information technologies to real projects for the recovery and dissemination of cultural heritage; and five other specific objectives. The transversal competencies: 1) Use of Technology, 2) Intellectual Curiosity and 3) Professional Impact. It was implemented in February - June 2022 with two student groups. A course was designed with concepts, lectures, activities and field immersion. The result was a positive development of competencies and the objectives were achieved. Nine multimedia productions were produced for the Historical Archive of the Archdiocese of Monterrey, the Museum of Sacred Art and the Basilica of Monterrey. This innovation was replicated with six more groups; in addition, the digitization of historical archives was added. Engineering students have achieved sensitivity and commitment to recover and promote cultural heritage. This didactic and research was nationally recognized as a Novus project and can be replicated in other universities.

Keywords: Interdisciplinarity, cultural heritage, technology, heritage.

1. Introduction

Currently, it is very necessary to establish a solid bridge between the needs of society and the teaching of the different engineering disciplines. This will be achieved through innovative didactic techniques that mark the future of the teaching/learning processes and the development of disciplinary and transversal competencies in future graduates. Simultaneously, in a globalized world, the cultural heritage of regions or collectives must be recovered, safeguarded and promoted in order to generate identity and a sense of life for present societies, and at the same time, respect for other cultural groups. That is why humanistic and citizenship training in future engineers is a very important complement within the curricula that is achieved by implementing active learning processes, and the definition and evaluation of the level of development of transversal competencies in students. This work shows the incorporation of humanistic and citizenship training courses for students of different engineering courses at Tec de Monterrey in real projects for the recovery, rescue and dissemination of cultural heritage and historical memory of their region. The innovation challenge has been to direct the use of technology with cultural heritage for the development of competencies. It had its origin, in turn, with another innovation called Week i: Craftsman of Music in 2018 and 2019, same (innovation) that was presented as a poster at the 7th. International Congress on Educational Innovation in 2020, and whose result is the following two links:

- Brief presentation, in Spanish: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=YXuwrqrMUPE&feature=youtu.be>
- Web page: <https://orfebresmusicales.wixsite.com/orfebresmusicalestec>

Week i consisted of an immersion of students from different careers to carry out a challenge for the development of competencies in only five days.

Phases and type of heritage for the challenge educational innovation project:

1. Week i September 2018: Sacred musical heritage. Musical craftsman: Jewels and musical treasures of the 19th century.
2. Week i October 2019: Secular musical heritage: Musical craftsman: Ode to nature.
3. February - June 2022: Artistic and architectural heritage. - Impact measurement was carried out in this semester.
4. August - December 2022: Documentary and bibliographic heritage with digitization of historical archives.

The third phase was in the semester February - June 2022 with two second semester groups of the subject Cultural imaginaries of Mexico. Subsequently this didactic has been carried out until 2024 with six more groups adding the digitization of historical archives.

This educational innovation changed from being one week in 2018 and 2019 to an entire semester starting in 2022 and distinguished as a Novus project. The design of this course, whose educational intention to incorporate technologies and interdisciplinarity to recover cultural heritage was recognized as a Novus Project of Educational Innovation, and within the top ten Novus courses across Tec de Monterrey nationwide. And what is a Novus project at Tec de Monterrey? According to the Institute for the Future of the Education - Novus of the Tecnológico de Monterrey (2022) Novus projects are courses designed in a disruptive way that have two axes: "firstly there is the educational innovation, the heart of the project, which will be implemented in one or more learning experiences; the second axis has to do with the experiment, which is oriented to formally measure the impact that the innovation has on some variable of educational or training interest". For this project, the "heart of the project" and challenge was to direct information technologies (ICTs) towards an area traditionally distant: cultural heritage for its recovery, rescue, valuation and promotion. This educational innovation will be explained in the following sequence: 2. Development, 2.1). Theoretical support of the didactic process, 2.2). Theoretical support of the academic discipline Cultural Heritage for the course Cultural Imaginaries of Mexico, 3) Implementation of the Innovation, 4) Evaluation of results, and 5) Conclusions.

2. Development

This educational innovation was implemented in the course Cultural Imaginaries of Mexico taught by the Department of Humanistic Studies to students of different engineering and professional careers of the Monterrey Campus of the Tecnológico de Monterrey during the semester February - June 2022. General objective: Incorporate the use of information technologies to real projects for the recovery and dissemination of the cultural heritage of Monterrey, Nuevo León, Mexico.

2.1 Theoretical and methodological basis of the didactic process and research.

The Tec de Monterrey Educational Model (2016) is based on the development of competencies and through challenge-based learning.

In this Model, competencies are understood as the conscious integration of knowledge, skills, attitudes and values that allow successfully facing both structured and uncertain situations and that may involve higher order mental processes. Competencies integrate both the knowledge and procedures of the discipline, as well as the attitudes and values that allow the formation of participative professionals committed to society. In the TEC21 Educational Model there are two categories of competencies: disciplinary and transversal. Disciplinary

competencies refer to all those knowledge, skills, attitudes and values that are considered necessary for professional practice. The development of disciplinary competencies implies a gradual construction that starts from the fundamental competencies to the terminal competencies of the discipline. On the other hand, transversal competencies are developed throughout the training process of any discipline, are useful for the graduate's life and have a direct impact on the quality of professional practice (6).

For this educational innovation it involved the following transversal competencies: 1) Intellectual curiosity, 2) Use of technology and 3). Professional impact. Following are the definitions (González et al., 2018):

1. Intellectual curiosity: Understood as a competence, intellectual curiosity should be framed, in line with the classification of, under the domain of the "Personal Knowledge Dimension", which refers to those traits of the individual's personality that guide his/her behavior and, consequently, have a determining influence on his/her autonomous actions and is closely related to the conduct and concrete actions of a person.
2. Domain of information and communication technologies (ICTs): Application of knowledge of the use of technology for the stated challenge.
3. Professional impact: Internalization of the objectives and competencies of the course for the short, medium and long term.

The Educational Model of Tec de Monterrey (2016) is implemented through active learning from a Challenge-Based Learning approach, defined as: "It is a pedagogical approach that actively involves the student in a real, relevant and environmentally relevant problematic situation, which involves the definition of a challenge and the implementation of a solution (10). Challenge-based learning is based on experiential learning, the principle of which is that students learn better when they actively participate in open learning experiences, instead of passively intervening in structured activities. In this sense, Experiential Learning offers students opportunities to apply what they learn in real situations, where they face problems, discover for themselves, try solutions and interact with other students within a given context (Moore, 2013). Experiential Learning is a holistic integrative approach to learning, combining experience, cognition and behavior (Akella, 2010). The identification of the challenges for the development of transversal competencies and learning experiences is done through a dialogue between the teaching team and the representatives of a public or private entity called "Training Partner" about the needs that the students would help to solve. A protocol or Academic Collaboration Agreement is signed, with the prior authorization of the Academic Department Direction, and then the general objective and specific objectives are defined, both for students and teachers (Akella, 2010).

Research assumption: "Students will develop to a greater extent the transversal competencies integrated into their curriculum by applying technology to recover and promote the cultural heritage of the city".

General objective: To incorporate the use of information technologies in real projects of recovery, rescue and cultural diffusion of Monterrey, Nuevo Leon, Mexico and the northeastern region of Mexico.

Specific objectives considered as challenges for the students were:

1. to carry out for the Training Partner creative multimedia or multiplatform productions to promote their cultural heritage both in form and content.
2. To develop the competencies of the Training Unit of Cultural Imaginaries of Mexico of the Tec de Monterrey during the February - June 2022 semester.

Specific objectives considered as challenges for teachers were:

3. To design innovative didactics specifically for this course inside and outside the classroom, and with immersions to workspaces for active learning from the approach of a Challenge Based Learning.
4. Obtain and analyze results with the two measurement instruments.
5. Identify areas of improvement for future projects of similar innovation.

Development and evaluation of competencies. How was the level of development of the three transversal competencies evaluated during the didactic process of the course and elaboration of the challenge? With three measurement instruments: a) Mainly with the measurement instrument proposed by (Adame and Olivares, 2018) for the development of the three competencies. b) Self-evaluation instruments coevaluation designed by the teachers, and c) Institutional Student Feedback Survey (ECO).

2.2 Theoretical basis of the academic discipline Cultural Heritage for the course Cultural Imaginaries of Mexico.

To overcome uncertainty, to build bridges between society and learning in the future, the environment close to the student and his community must be an instrument of teaching, learning and development of competencies to trigger cultural identity, memory and encounter with the cultural other. In the design of this didactic, the competencies to be developed must be identified and in a quantitative way demonstrate its formative impact for the possibility of replicating this didactic in more students (Gutiérrez, V.M et al 2017 and 2018). We agree with Innovation and Social Entrepreneurship in Higher Education Institutions: Students4Change (2019) when considering relevant for the training of current entrepreneurs and social leaders, it is necessary to promote experiences in students [and teachers] that give testimony of social entrepreneurship and leadership whose actions benefit the present society and preserve the memory. What is the teacher's role in contrast to other educational models? From this perspective, the role of the traditional teacher is now also that of an advisor who shows confidence and respect for the diverse possibilities of development of each of his or her students, which moves him or her to seek the most effective way for them to achieve integral development (Ayala, 2002).

To understand the concept, recovery and safeguarding of cultural heritage, the following concepts are relevant to approach this innovation: culture, encounter with the other and cultural instruments.

The definition of culture by Gómez (Pérez, 2000) is used: "Culture refers to the common system of life of a people, which is the result of its history, of the adaptation between that human population and the environment in which it lives, and socially transmitted, a process that is carried out through productive techniques, through organizational structures at the economic, social and political levels, and through conceptions of life, of a scientific, mythological, ethical, religious, etc. type. Therefore, I define culture globally, embracing all the levels that compose the social system, in its complexity, interrelated among themselves, operating in a conscious and unconscious way". Regarding the Encounter with the other, according to Reyes Heróles (2003), knowing one's own culture and that of others is a way to conquer freedom. In the same way, inquiring into memory, into the past through cultural heritage in its different modalities, is an encounter with the other, that other of other centuries, of other generations, but who left a legacy for us in our present, to find our own identity; that self in search of meaning. Thus, this experience will propitiate the yearning to conquer freedom through our own knowledge of our cultural heritage and, in turn, of the other culturally different.

Cultural instruments. And how is culture constructed and perpetuated? Bonfil's methodological proposal (1987) proposes the concept of cultural instruments as a way to know a certain culture, because identifying them will give greater meaning to their presence and function. Cultural instrument: "Any collective act with a common social purpose, and they are pertinent to analyze a social group" (108) and can be identified or created within a cultural group: They are material, demographic: of organization: of knowledge, symbolic and of communication and emotional or subjective. They are of interest for the recovery of time, knowledge, space, speech and identity; and the synthesis of the previous recoveries for a reflection on the historical project of each cultural group.

This educational innovation is integrated to the interest of other colleagues in different parts of the world to use the different modalities of technologies with the same purpose: to value cultural heritage; as stated in Diaz, C. et al (2021) citing at least six cases, in addition to the one they expose: "Recently, digitalization has also permeated the reactivation of cultural heritage. The joining of Augmented Reality (AR) and digital cultural content has produced examples of recovery and revival of cultural heritage in Latin America and the world. It is a new area for these applications; cultural, heritage, and historical societies and museums have taken advantage of this technology to represent contents and uses. Augmented reality provides an excellent orientation and immersion of the user (tourist, visitor, or citizen) in the destination or the patrimonial or tourist resource. The user perceives information about the place being visited in a more real and interactive way". In turn, UNESCO (2014) in its Indicators of Culture for Development (IUCD) project "considers culture not only as a sector of activity, but also in terms of the values and norms that guide human action". To be aware that culture in its different manifestations generates cultural heritage so that its valuation is a guide to preserve the identity of all people in order to identify the meaning of our lives.

3. Implementation of Educational Innovation

For this educational innovation, teachers are committed to measure or investigate the impact on students with a data collection instrument for later analysis. In Table 1. Instrument for measuring the three selected transversal competencies in pretest and posttest, the instrument with the three selected transversal competencies in pretest and posttest is shown. From the instrument proposed by (Olivares, and Adame, 2018). Seven questions were selected from the 40 that the instrument must measure the impact and development of the three selected transversal competencies, and a survey was used for their measurement. This survey was answered individually; each question had an answer with a scale from 1 to 5, where 1 is the value that represents the least development of the competency: "totally disagree", and 5 is value that represents the highest development of the competency: "totally agree".

The table 1 below shows the three transversal competencies selected from the instrument and the questions that were written to measure the level of development of the cross-cutting competencies or variables of this research.

Table 1. Instrument for measuring three selected transversal competencies and their questions in pre-test and post-test.

Transversal competence	Pre-test	Post-test
1. Intellectual curiosity	I expect the selected activity to challenge me intellectually.	The activity challenged me intellectually.
	I expect to solve problems relevant to my professional development during the immersion semester.	I solved problems relevant to my professional development.
	I spend time searching for information to learn new topics.	I spent time searching for information to learn about the topic related to the activity.
2. Use of technology	I expect to make use of technology in challenging activities.	I had the opportunity to make use of technology in the challenging activity.
	Time and resources are used efficiently in the projects.	Time and resources were used efficiently.
	I developed creative solutions to complex problems.	I developed creative solutions to challenging activities in this immersive semester.
3. Professional impact	The organizations I have been involved with have benefited from my actions.	The organization we participated with benefited from our actions.

Table 2. Chronology of the didactic process February - June 2022, shows the general schedule of the Novus course - Cultural Imaginaries of Mexico: February / June 2022.

Fifteen weeks of work divided into three periods of five. 40 students in nine teams with four or five members. The master classes are sessions with experts of recognized academic and professional trajectory, six were organized. Three didactically guided visits inside and outside the Campus to the spaces required for the project.

Table 2. Chronology of the didactic process February - June 2022. Names of invited persons marked with "XXX".

Period 1	Period 2	Period 3 - Workshop
Weeks 1 to 5	Weeks 6 to 10	Weeks 11 to 15
<p>Pre-test application.</p> <p>Contents: Readings, concepts and learning activities and development of competencies per week.</p> <p>Academic visits to: Museum of Mexican History, Museum of the Northeast, Museum of Contemporary Art, and to White Space- space for reflection (within the Campus).</p> <p>Master class, 3/6:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. XXX, PhD and Poet from Edge Hill University - UK. 2. XXX, B.A. in Communication Sciences (ExATec LCC) 1988 and M.A. in Education. Artist and cultural promoter, social entrepreneur. 3. Priest XXX, Director of the Historical Archive and Archdiocesan Museum of Sacred Art, and training partner. 	<p>Content: Readings, concepts and learning and competency development activities per week.</p> <p>Immersion 1 in workspace. Explanation by teachers, specialists and training partner of the spaces and objects of study. Sessions at different times for the convenience of student groups.</p> <p>Teacher XXX, curator and responsible for the Archdiocesan Museum of Sacred Art.</p> <p>Priest XXX, Rector of the Basilica of Our Lady of Monterrey.</p> <p>Immersion 2: Visit only students for integration as work teams, assimilation of knowledge, interaction with spaces, objects of study and people involved in these spaces.</p> <p>Master class, 3/6:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 4. XXX: BA in History from the Faculty of Philosophy and Letters of UNAM, master and PhD candidate in Mesoamerican Studies 2. 5. XXX, Dr. in Hispanic Letters, Lic. in Hispanic Letters Ex A Tec, and expert in paleontology and researcher and promoter of Digital Humanities. Project advisor 6. XXX, B.A. in Communication Sciences ExATec 2003, and M.A. in Humanistic Studies. Co-editor and content generator in the communication media of Campus Monterrey Conecta (https://conecta.tec.mx/es) and other institutional channels. 	<p>Counseling and guidance to the group of students throughout these weeks in and out of the classroom.</p> <p>Pre-production</p> <p>Production</p> <p>Post-production</p> <p>Project presentation: nine multiplatform productions.</p> <p>Post test application.</p>

The results includes the following 9 multimedia productions developed by 9 teams for the Training Partner:

1. 360 Virtual Tour - Basilica of Our Lady of Monterrey. <https://roundme.com/tour/867808/view/2719367/>
2. Virtual catalog of the exhibition Costuras del cielo: El ajuar de la Virgen del Roble.
3. https://www.canva.com/design/DAFCxoOiulYjQbfjiUVxhdehR4rB9bL3g/view?utm_content=DAFCxoOiulY&utm_campaign=designshare&utm_medium=link2&utm_source=sharebutton
4. Animation of the history of the Virgin of Monterrey. Duration 4.33. <https://youtu.be/G7SKfxvFsCk>
5. Electronic page - Catalog of works of the Archdiocesan Museum of Sacred Art. <https://a011777515.wixsite.com/website>
6. Documentary Basilica of Our Lady of Monterrey. Duration 2.49. <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=7lh2gNTCJO0>
7. Documentary of the Archdiocesan Museum of Sacred Art. Duration 13.02 minutes. <https://youtu.be/lbdCLjAslxY>
8. History of the Virgin of Monterrey. Duration 3.23 minutes <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=U62Rzbp5Lg&list=LL&index=3&t=7s>
9. The dresses of the Virgin of Monterrey. Duration 6.31. <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=jEclQEN-7uk&list=LL&index=2>
10. Documentary on the Basilica of Our Lady of Monterrey. Duration 3.23 seconds. <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=X0AimxhkEc4&list=LL&index=1>

4. Results evaluation

The initial research assumption: "Students will develop to a greater extent the transversal competencies integrated to their curriculum by applying technology to recover and promote the cultural heritage of the city" was favorably verified with the instrument measuring the development of transversal competencies (Olivares, 2018). The values were in a range from 1: totally disagree, to 5: totally agree. 40 students applied the pre-test and 20 the post-test; to analyze the results, those who answered it at both moments, before and after, were identified: they were 16 students.

Results analysis process:

- Pres test: in each question the accumulated points of the answers with 4 and 5 frequencies were added up.
- Post test: in each question, the accumulated points of the answers with 4 and 5 frequencies of the same question were added.
- Comparative: the before and after of the accumulated points were compared.
- Analysis of results.

From the beginning of the course, high expectations were reflected in all aspects, since answers with 4 and 5 in all of them added up to +10/16 frequencies.

In all the questions, the number of frequencies with 4 and 5 points of the pre-test was surpassed, to be reflected in the higher number of frequencies with 4 and 5 points of the post-test.

Comprehensively, the transversal competencies had a higher number in the post-test: (1) Intellectual curiosity +3; (2) Use of technology +4; (3) Professional impact +5.

The level of expectations for the course was maintained and exceeded and was reflected in the level of commitment of the students to the solution of the challenges agreed upon at the beginning of the semester.

Table 3. Comparative pre-test and post-test of the instrument for measuring the development of transversal competencies by question and a general one.

	1	2	3	4	5	Result: sum of answers with 4 and 5	Difference pre / post
1. Intellectual curiosity Pre test	0	3	2	11	0	11	-
1. Intellectual curiosity Post test	0	0	2	6	8	14	+3
Pre - I expect the selected activity to challenge me intellectually	0	1	1	5	9	14	-
Post - The activity challenged me intellectually.	0	0	0	6	10	16	+2
Pre - I expect to solve problems relevant to my professional development during the immersion semester.	1	0	0	2	13	15	-
Post - I solved problems relevant to my professional development.	0	0	0	3	13	15	+1
Pre - I spend time searching for information to learn new topics.	0	2	1	4	9	13	-
Post - I spent time searching for information to learn about the topic related to the activity.	0	0	1	2	13	15	+2
2. Use of Technology Pres test	0	0	6	8	2	10	-
2. Use of Technology Post test	0	0	0	13	3	16	+4

Pre - I expect to make use of technology in challenging activities.	0	0	1	0	15	15	-
Post - I had the opportunity to make use of technology in the challenging activity.	0	0	0	3	13	16	+1
Pre - Time and resources are used efficiently in the projects.	0	2	2	5	6	11	-
Post - Time and resources were used efficiently.	0	0	0	6	10	16	+5
Pre - I developed creative solutions to complex problems.	0	0	2	3	11	14	-
Post - I developed creative solutions to challenging activities in this immersive semester.	0	0	0	4	12	16	+2
3. Professional impact Pre test	0	2	4	3	7	10	-
3. Professional impact Post test	0	0	1	3	12	15	+5
Pre - The organizations I have been involved with have benefited from my actions.	0	2	4	3	7	10	-
Post - The organization we participated with benefited from our actions.	0	0	1	3	12	15	+5

ECO.A. In the institutional student feedback survey on the subject (ECO.A), the result was 9.28/10, and with comments from the students written voluntarily gratifying about this experience and very encouraging for the teaching team.

The training partner declared his satisfaction with the productions:

June 30, 2022

"Dear professor Gerardo:

I am surprised by the excellent work that the Tec students did, from me they all have a 100 for their effort, dedication and creativity and I thank them for collaborating with me on this project. I hope that in the future we can continue working on something as valuable as our history, that of the city and that of the Virgen del Roble

I remain infinitely grateful and at your service in Christ.

Rector XXX, Basilica of Our Lady of the Roble. Monterrey, Mexico."

Spontaneous student testimony:

May 13, 2022

"Thank you for everything taught during the course, teacher. We take more than class information with us. It inspires us to continue creating in our own way, without forgetting our roots and the works of generations who were looking for the same thing as us... a space in this [world] to shine." Andrés XXX, student."

Additionally, it is interesting to note that a grandmother, four mothers, a brother and four friends joined the visits with the students.

5. Conclusions

The general objective of the research and the five specific objectives presented at the beginning of this work were achieved, thus validating, and consolidating the didactic design and implementation of this educational innovation. In all educational innovation and research, measurement instruments are essential to validate the results of the teaching/learning process and the development of competencies. It is suggested to replicate it with more groups of engineering students in more universities to join projects of recovery, rescue and dissemination of historical, artistic and cultural heritage of a city, region or community from all professions. Interdisciplinarity is important for the safeguarding of cultural heritage, both for the personal and professional

formation of the student, as well as for the current society in Mexico. The competencies must be very well related in the formation of people to detonate the commitment with the recovery, rescue and promotion of cultural heritage, as well as with the encounter of a personal identity from an approach of the "I in search of meaning" and thus move to the approach of "The encounter with the cultural other". Following this research, the didactic model has been implemented with six additional groups and four different training partners.

It is important to consolidate this educational innovation project as an imprint for the memory, preservation and dissemination of our artistic legacy and respect for its proponents; as a sign that guides the current artistic inspiration as a source of cultural identity for a comprehensive community development; and a symbol of union between artists and cultural promoters of several centuries with a common purpose: to identify the region as an international artistic reference. In this 21st century, it is up to us to attend to their commission; and to continue preserving, cultivating and strengthening this valuable legacy; replicating this model in many cities is an opportune educational alternative for this noble purpose to overcome uncertainty: to build bridges between society and learning in the future. In future research we will request the application of the necessary pre-test and post-test instrument of the course and achieve an investigation.

The Novus Educational Innovation Project - Tec de Monterrey (2023) experience is shared in Spanish in the following video, developed by Gerardo González Lara, Carolina Sacristán Ramírez: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=bCvyJ3wZYEI>

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